

FUNCTIONAL-SEMANTIC STUDY OF ROBOTICS TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract: This study examines the functional and semantic characteristics of robotics terminology in English and Uzbek languages. It highlights differences in term usage, semantic structures, and translation challenges, emphasizing the impact of cultural and linguistic factors. The findings reveal that while English terms are precise and standardized, Uzbek equivalents often rely on neologisms and loanwords, leading to semantic shifts. The study underscores the need for standardized frameworks to enhance the clarity and effectiveness of robotics terminology in multilingual contexts.

Keywords. Robotics terminology, functional analysis, semantic analysis, English, Uzbek, translation challenges, linguistic standardization.

The field of robotics has undergone significant growth in recent years, with its applications expanding across various industries such as manufacturing, healthcare, and artificial intelligence. As a result, the need for precise and standardized terminology has become increasingly important to ensure clear communication among engineers, researchers, and practitioners worldwide. This study focuses on the functional and semantic aspects of robotics terminology, specifically comparing the English and Uzbek languages. By examining the roles, meanings, and translation challenges of key terms, this research aims to shed light on the linguistic intricacies that arise when adapting robotics terminology across languages, highlighting both the technical and cultural factors that influence its use and understanding.[7]

The study of robotics terminology intersects multiple domains, including linguistics, engineering, and cognitive science. A review of existing literature reveals significant efforts to understand and develop terminological frameworks in robotics,

driven by the rapid pace of technological advancements and the global nature of the field.

Robotics terminology has evolved alongside technological progress, with early contributions focused on the mechanical and electronic components of robots. Studies by Asimov (1965) laid a foundational understanding of robotics, coining the term "robotics" itself[1]. Since then, researchers have expanded the scope of terminology to encompass artificial intelligence, machine learning, and autonomous systems, reflecting the field's growing complexity.

Functional analysis examines how robotics terms operate within technical contexts, focusing on their roles in describing mechanical functions, computational processes, and interactive systems. Studies by scholars such as Albus (1981) highlight the semantic precision required to describe complex systems like robotic manipulators and sensory feedback loops.[2] Moreover, cognitive linguistics has been applied to analyze the metaphorical extensions of robotics terminology, such as the use of terms like "intelligence" or "learning" in non-human contexts.

The semantic aspect of robotics terminology presents unique challenges. Terms often originate in one language or culture, such as English, and require adaptation or translation into others, which can lead to ambiguity or loss of meaning. Scholars like Cabré (1999) and Bowker (2002) have discussed the implications of terminology in specialized languages, emphasizing the need for precision and contextual understanding.[3,4]

The methodology for this study is designed to comprehensively analyze the functional and semantic features of robotics terminology in both English and Uzbek languages. The research employs a combination of qualitative and comparative methods, grounded in linguistic analysis, to achieve the following objectives:

Examine the functional roles of robotics terminology in technical discourse; Identify semantic structures and patterns in the use of these terms; Compare and contrast the terminological frameworks in English and Uzbek.

The analysis of robotics terminology in both English and Uzbek revealed notable differences in functional roles and semantic structures. In English, terms like

"robot," "sensor," and "actuator" function as foundational concepts, with their meanings often extending metaphorically to describe complex systems. For instance, "robot" originates from the Czech word "robota," meaning "forced labor," and has evolved to encompass a wide range of autonomous machines.[5] In contrast, Uzbek terminology frequently incorporates loanwords or neologisms, such as "robototexnika" (robotics), which may not always convey the full semantic depth of the original English terms. This discrepancy can lead to challenges in accurately translating and understanding technical documents between the two languages.[6]

The comparative study also highlighted the impact of cultural and linguistic factors on the adoption and adaptation of robotics terminology in Uzbek. While English terms often retain their original meanings across various contexts, Uzbek equivalents sometimes undergo semantic shifts or are used in specific contexts that may not align perfectly with their English counterparts. For example, the term "intelligence" in English is commonly associated with human cognitive abilities, whereas in Uzbek, "aqlli" can refer to both human intelligence and the functionality of smart devices. Such nuances underscore the importance of context and cultural understanding in the translation and application of robotics terminology. Addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort to develop standardized terminological frameworks that consider both linguistic precision and cultural relevance, thereby facilitating effective communication in the field of robotics.

Conclusion

This study explored the functional and semantic dimensions of robotics terminology in English and Uzbek, highlighting key differences and challenges in translation, adaptation, and usage. The findings reveal that English robotics terms are well-established, often carrying metaphorical and technical precision, whereas their Uzbek counterparts rely on neologisms and loanwords, occasionally lacking the same depth and consistency. These differences underscore the influence of cultural and linguistic factors in shaping technical terminology, presenting unique challenges for effective cross-linguistic communication.

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